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THEORETICAL OBSERVATIONS ON THE EXISTENCE OF DEFENSE MECHANISMS IN THE PERSON

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Psychoanalytically, psychological defense mechanisms were studied by Z. Freud, A. Freud, E. Fromm, K. Horney and others. Z. Freud used the term "defense" for the first time in his work "defensive neuropsychoses" (1896). In these works, Z. Freud fully expressed the purpose and content of defense mechanisms. Later, he continued in the articles "The Concept of Depression", "Beyond the Pleasure Principle", "Public Psychology" and "I" analysis, "I" and "He" and replaced the term "defense" with "depression" by Z. Freud. In the appendix to the work "Depression, Symptom and Anxiety", Freud emphasized his old concept of defense, which is still used in the scientific literature, and gave specific concepts to other defense mechanisms.

In this way, the goal of phenomenology and the subject of psychological protection are determined. We can find a number of thoughts on this problem in Z. Freud's article "Finite and Infinite Analysis". In this article, as products of the development and mastery of defense mechanisms, the dialectical generalization of internal-external conflicts is presented "as a common name for all mechanisms" that regulate individual behavior. That is, events are connected with the main functions of the psyche. It is almost no different from the last works of Z. Freud. His work attempted to create a general theoretical system of defense mechanisms. In his seminal monograph published in 1936, he gave a comprehensive account of the various styles of defensive action. According to A. Freud, defense mechanisms are based on 2 types of reactions:

1. Blocking the manifestation of impulses in conscious action.
2. To distort them to such an extent that their previous intensity is sufficiently reduced or they flow in the other direction [2].

A. Freud distinguishes a number of criteria for the classification of defense mechanisms. For example, the localization of the danger of "I", the time of cognition in ontogeny, the level of constructiveness, and the last criterion form its further development, the division of defense mechanisms into primary and secondary, primitive and advanced, less and more conscious, adaptive and non-

adaptive. He developed Z.Freud's idea of the connection between the main methods of defense and corresponding neuroses, and determined the role in the norm and pathology of individual development.

And finally, A.Freud defines the concepts of defense mechanisms. "Defensive mechanisms are the activities of the "I", which appear when the "I" that is a danger to him falls into excessive activity or corresponding affects. They function without the consent of the mind. In these concepts, the important idea of what we know as automatism is put forward, to bring defenses to the appropriate type of unconscious phenomena. Similarly, it is appropriate to raise the question of comparing the conscious to the unconscious in the organization of protective processes. Any subjectively impossible spiritual content must be understood as such, even if only for a short time before being transformed or destroyed. After that, simple mental operations are solved, strengthened and acquire a conditioned reflex, unstable, automatic character. Thus, in addition to determining the time source of the ontogenetic structure, the adaptation values of the defense mechanisms, A. Freud differentiated the unconscious of the mental material that is influenced by the unconscious of defense and the defense process [1].

A. Freud understands defense more broadly than Z. Freud, he emphasizes that it can be used not only against interests, but also against all things that cause danger. The classification he proposed is based on the 10 defense mechanisms proposed by his father. The first five of them are repression, regression, formation of reactions, isolation and elimination. Z. Seen by Freud as defense techniques used in attachment neuroses; introjection and projection are described as "neurotic mechanisms" – in unhealthy changes based on jealousy, paranoia and homosexuality "Self-defense methods; self-struggle and appeal explained as "instinct transformation", sublimation or substitution of instinctive goals - a protective method suitable for the study of norms, not neuroses. Among the 10 methods of defense, Anna Freud added 5 more, less important and related to a certain period of personality development, that is, aggression, identification, activism, intellectualization, limitation of the "I", fantasy.

Starting with Z.Freud, in the subsequent works of experts, who studied the mechanisms of psychological defense, it was repeatedly emphasized that the defense in normal conditions of a person, taking the form of fixed defense, which has the ability to strengthen in extreme, critical, stressful life conditions, has been repeatedly emphasized. This person's driving of internal conflicts can turn into an

unconscious source of dissatisfaction with himself and those around him, as well as enable the emergence of special limits, called coping by Z.Freud [1].

Different manifestations of psychology directions, although they do not agree in the concept of personal protection mechanisms as an integral and integral characteristic of an individual, they are divided into different approaches in their view of the source of the conflicts that cause them to move. If in the concept of Z.Freud - "He", "I" and "Super Man" is considered an internal conflict of opposites, K. Jung connects the protective means of the person, the demands of the external environment and the main typological institutions of the individual with mutual incompatibility. K. Horney - at the same time connects the individual to incompatible neurotic requirements that urge people to strive, show aggression towards them and the desire not to submit to them. G. Sullivan is associated with the conflicting demands of complex interpersonal relationships. Let's briefly touch on the main concepts presented above.

According to psychologist K. G. Jung, the main forces of the unconscious are the archetypes of the "collective unconscious". In particular,

- firstly, as an element of general information space;
- secondly, individualized instinct.

K. Jung connects the manifestation of personal protection with the incompatibility of the requirements of the external environment and the main typological institutions of the individual. The basic principle of A. Adler's theory is the principle of activity and development called "individual psychology". As a source of conflicts that activate defense mechanisms, A. Adler describes the opposition between two unconscious opposing tendencies, that is, the feeling of incompleteness and the desire for dominance. While distinguishing the main phenomena of psychoanalysis about the leading role of the unconscious, K. Horney paid attention to the ontogenesis of the natural and social person and the social environment that affects the formation of the personality. He sees the "basal conflict" as the basis of the conflict. At the beginning of any conflict lies the individual's relationship with other people, over time it affects the whole person [3].

To date, there is no information about the exact amount of the defense mechanism in any branch of psychology. In addition to internal protections of a person, interpersonal protections are also distinguished. R. Plutchik, H. Kellerman, H. R. Kontellar offered an interesting review of the types of psychological protection. There are also unique opinions on the classification of defense mechanisms into groups. Some authors suggest dividing them into primary and secondary. The

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default can include rejection, compression. Rationalization, substitution, reactions to the secondary [1].

It can be seen from the mentioned points that the formation of protective mechanisms in a person literally makes it possible to prevent conflicting situations that arise with them. Also, by acquiring information about defense mechanisms, a person will be able to plan and manage his life path.

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